

EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

About this machine-actionable data management plan (maDMP)

The open maDMP will serve as the reference framework for all data-related activities—collection, processing, generation, and storage—within the Horizon Europe EU-CHINA BRIDGE project (Grant Agreement No. 101137971). Hosted in ARGOS, the maDMP outlines every dataset to be created, managed, and curated over the course of the project. These datasets will be deposited in the project’s Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge/>) and directly linked within the ARGOS maDMP.

In addition, a dedicated report (D7.6) will be released in September 2024, providing general guidance for all project datasets. This includes an overview of the expected data, principles for FAIR data handling, data security practices, necessary resources, and ethical considerations. The report will be revised annually and will act as a practical guide for consortium partners, supporting them in managing their datasets and ensuring that the maDMP in ARGOS is kept up to date with proper descriptions and metadata.

About the project

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and

China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy

intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated

assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and

comprehensive emissions data. It will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing

dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts. It will deliver two open-

source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron &

steel and chemical industries, two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China, and

co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions. It will also

develop the most up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived

climate pollutant emission inventories as well as dynamic monitoring of key emission sources at high

spatiotemporal granularity. A state-of-the-art modelling framework will be developed, exploiting and

advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions data,

representing technology and policy options, enabling assessment of socioeconomic impacts, covering multiple

economic sectors and regions, and offering high spatial and technology detail. The enhanced models will be

used to co-produce net-zero pathways for the EU and China, explicitly assessing co-benefits and trade-offs of

climate policies with other societal goals while exploring cooperation policies and governance to drive the

global transformation and assessing the distributional and global-level implications of the two regions'

decarbonisation. The pathways will be documented in new workspaces in the I2AM PARIS platform.

Funded by the European Union

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

EU-CHINA-BRIDGE

Researchers

Organizations

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [EU-CHINA BRIDGE - Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan](#)

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Researchers:

Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [EU-CHINA-BRIDGE](#)

Project: [EU-CHINA-BRIDGE](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

EU-CHINA BRIDGE: D3.1 – Two EU-China technology inventories on promising low-emission technology options for EIIs

Two technology inventories for promising low-emission technologies in the steel and petrochemical industries. These inventories are developed as part of the EU-CHINA BRIDGE project (funded by the Horizon Europe programme), in support of the transition to climate-neutral industries in Europe and China. The inventories contain detailed descriptive and quantitative data on selected breakthrough technologies, including their technology readiness level (TRL) and development status. The technologies were selected based on criteria such as net-zero compatibility and high CO₂ reduction potential.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The data are generated by EU-CHINA-BRIDGE research

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Data derived from literature review.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values (CSV)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

12.6 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

To keep information in a useful format so it can be used by simulation models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data derived from literature review.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

Data can be used by simulation models by researchers in IAM modelling teams. Also provide useful information about Steel and Petrochemical Industry. Information can be used by decision makers and

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Data have been given a DOI by Zenodo.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

In Zenodo

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed through the European OpenAIRE initiative and managed by CERN.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo will automatically register a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for a record once you publish it.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

EU-CHINA BRIDGE: D3.1 – Two EU-China technology inventories on promising low-emission technology options for EIIs

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

It is open publicly in Zenodo.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

The data are in csv file format so whatever excel-like editor, python IDE with pandas library loaded or R IDE, would suffice to access and query the data.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data are presented on the website of IAM PARIS platform and will be used in research.

<https://iamparis.eu/>

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Georgios Xexakis (0000-0002-5459-2166)

Data Manager

b. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Stratis Alexandrou (0009-0007-4128-9815)

Data Manager

c. Ole Zelt (0000-0001-5427-6406)

Author/Researcher

d. Ylva Kloo (0000-0002-5918-3919)

Author/Researcher

e. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Alexander Jülich

Author/Researcher

f. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Svenja Theisen

Author/Researcher

g. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Hui Kong

Author/Researcher

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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